

Effect of Titania on the Dehydration Kinetics of 12-(Calcium oxide)-7-(aluminium oxide) Hydrates

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12-(Calcium oxide)-7-(aluminium oxide), i.e. $C_{12}A_7$ is almost always present in variable proportions upto 15% in the ordinary high alumina cements and the more refractory calcium aluminate cements. The thermal stability of $C_{12}A_7$ hydrate in relation to titania has been studied by thermogravimetry. The dehydration rate curves obtained at different temperatures (100–400°) follow first order kinetics. The activation energy values of the dehydration reactions are found to be dependent on the titania content. A 6% titania has beneficial role on the thermal stability of the hydrated $C_{12}A_7$.

$C_{12}A_7$ like other calcium aluminates, hydrates to form metastable hexagonal compound CAH_{10} which gradually converts first to CAH_8 and alumina gel and finally to stable cubic C_3AH_6 . This conversion is associated with strength reduction and several precautions including the use of low water : cement ratio, hydration temperature and humidity are recommended to retard the conversion rate. It is well known that the hexagonal hydrate CAH_{10} can not be permanently stabilised by any of the physical means² or through chemical additives³. It has been suggested⁴ that the stability of CAH_{10} phase may be improved by incorporating calcium silicate hydrates during the hydration of CA through the formation of C_2ASH_8 (stratlingite). It is indicated that the activation energy values of the dehydration reactions of the hydrated calcium aluminates and high alumina cements may be utilised in explaining the stability of hydrated compounds⁵. Titania normally present in high-alumina cement is CT (perovskite) whose beneficial effect on cement properties has been reported⁶. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the effect of titania on the dehydration kinetics of hydrated $C_{12}A_7$.

Results and Discussion

The chemical compositions of the samples are shown in Table 1. Free lime of the samples were

*Notation : C = CaO, A = Al_2O_3 , H = H_2O , S = SiO_2 , T = TiO_2 .

within 0.2% by weight. The results reveal that Al_2O_3 has been gradually replaced by TiO_2 , keeping the CaO content fixed.

TABLE 1— CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE PREPARED CALCIUM ALUMINATES

Sample no.	Composition (% by wt)		
	Al_2O_3	CaO	TiO_2
1	51.52	48.48	—
2	49.50	48.44	1.98
3	47.48	48.46	4.05
4	45.52	48.40	6.02

The variation of compressive strength with curing time at room temperature is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2— COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH IN RELATION TO CURING TIME OF DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Curing time/day	Compressive strength ($kg\ cm^{-2}$)			
	1	2	3	4
8 h	75.42	94.28	94.28	94.28
1	84.18	150.85	131.30	113.14
3	131.30	131.30	131.30	113.14
7	131.30	113.14	113.14	113.14
14	113.14	94.28	94.28	127.96
28	113.14	94.28	94.28	131.14

It is evident that for all the samples the strength gradually decreased after 7 days curing except the sample containing 6% TiO_2 where the strength gradually improved after 7 days curing. Because 6% TiO_2 improved the strength retaining capacity of

CAH₁₀, it might be said that the presence of TiO₂, has some effect on the stabilisation of CAH₁₀.

Weight-loss vs time plots for all the four hydrated C₁₂A₇ samples exhibited exponential behaviour, indicating the possibility of first order kinetics. As the nature of curves for all the samples was identical, only the curves for sample 1 are shown (Fig. 1). At a fixed temperature, if L_t is the weight-loss

Fig 1. Weight-loss vs time plots at different temperatures for C₁₂A₇ hydrated for 3 days.

at time t , and L_∞ the total weight-loss at infinite time (L_∞), then $L_\infty - L_t$ is the concentration of water remaining in the sample at time t and according to first order kinetics, the rate of dehydration will be

$$\frac{dL_t}{dt} = K(L_\infty - L_t) \quad (1)$$

The method originally suggested by Guggenheim and followed by Murray and White⁷ may also be adopted. This method involves the use of the equation,

$$\log \Delta L = -\frac{Kt}{2.303} + \log [L_\infty \{1 - \exp(-K\Delta t)\}] \quad (2)$$

where ΔL is the difference between the weight-loss

at time $(t + \Delta t)$ and that at time t , the time interval Δt between the two sets of readings being kept fixed at a value greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. The values of L_∞ calculated by this method do not differ substantially from the direct experimental determination using equation (1).

In the present investigation, L values were taken from direct experimental determination, and dehydration at a particular temperature has been assumed to be complete when weight-loss became 0.0002 g in 5 min or even lower. Plots of $\log [(L_\infty - L_t)/L_\infty]$ vs time at different temperatures for hydrated C₁₂A₇ samples are shown in Fig. 2. The rate constants of dehydration (K) at different temperatures were calculated from the slopes and the values are given in Table 3. The limits of applicability of the first order law as determined from the linearity of plots (Fig. 2) varied from 63 to 93%.

The activation energy values of the dehydration reaction of hydrated C₁₂A₇ calculated from the Arrhenius equation are as follows : sample no. 1, 2942; no. 2, 2452; no. 3, 3558; no. 4, 3519; cal g-mol⁻¹. The activation energy values of the samples indicate that TiO₂ upto 2% reduces the thermal stability. The activation energies of samples containing 4 and 6% TiO₂ are very close to each other indicating almost similar thermal stability but considering the compressive strength retaining capacity after 14 days curing it can be concluded that the presence of TiO₂ (6% by wt) had beneficial effect on the curing strength and the thermal stability of hydrated C₁₂A₇.

TABLE 3- RATE CONSTANTS OF DEHYDRATION (K) OF HYDRATED C₁₂A₇ IN RELATION TO TEMPERATURE

Sample no	K (min ⁻¹) at temperatures (°C)				
	100	200	300	400	500
1	0.1011	0.2488	0.3104	0.3507	0.4864
2	0.1162	0.2487	0.3069	0.3836	0.4221
3	0.0870	0.2223	0.2517	0.3396	0.5445
4	0.0718	0.1725	0.2524	0.3536	0.5515

Experimental

The calcium aluminates were prepared from chemically pure (B.D.H.) Ca(OH)₂, Al(OH)₃ and TiO₂.

Fig. 2. Isothermal dehydration rate curves for $C_{12}A_7$, $C_{12}A_7 + 2\% TiO_2$, $C_{12}A_7 + 4\% TiO_2$ and $C_{12}A_7 + 6\% TiO_2$.

They were dry-mixed in a pot mill after the required proportioning. The mixture was then shaped in the form of small balls using water as binder. The balls were dried, fired at 1380° for 2 h, then crushed and ground in a steel pot mill to a fineness of about $0.32 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. X-Ray diffraction patterns of the synthetic aluminates confirmed the presence of $C_{12}A_7$ as the main constituent, although traces of other aluminates were also detected in each sample.

The compressive strengths were measured by the method adopted by Parker⁸. The mortar consisted of calcium aluminate and grog (ISI Brick No. 8, - 80 + 120 BS sieve) in the proportion of 1 : 3 by weight. L.25 cm cube briquettes were prepared using (*W/c* ratio 0.5). The compressive strength was measured in a manually operated hydraulic press.

The hydrated material (1 g), obtained after the

compressive strength test, was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis to monitor the dehydration characteristics of hydrated calcium aluminate. The temperature was accurate within $\pm 0.5^\circ$.

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